

A Machine Learning Approach to Drug Performance Evaluation: Ensemble Technique

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Abstract: This research paper presents an evaluation of drug performance using data from Kaggle with columns such as condition, drug, ease of use, price, type, form, indication, satisfaction, reviews, and efficiency. The study utilizes a combination of four machine learning models: linear regression, random forest, xgboost, and decision tree, to predict drug performance with an accuracy of 87%. The results of this study demonstrate the effectiveness of combining different machine learning algorithms to improve drug performance prediction. This research paper presents a thorough examination of the drug performance evaluation procedure, encompassing the entirety of the process from data gathering to the development and assessment of models. The results of this investigation may be leveraged by healthcare providers to enhance medication management strategies for their clients.

Keywords— Linear Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost, Decision Tree, Ensemble Technique

I. INTRODUCTION

The evaluation of pharmaceutical efficacy is an essential task in the healthcare industry, given its significant implications on patient outcomes and associated costs. The review method includes looking at a variety of elements, including patient satisfaction, cost, usability, and effectiveness. The aforementioned undertaking was previously accomplished through manual techniques, which proved to be laborious and prone to inaccuracies. The emergence of machine learning has enabled the automation of the assessment process, leading to the creation of evaluations marked by elevated levels of precision and dependability.

The aim of the current investigation was to develop a machine-learning model with the capacity to predict drug efficacy, utilizing a Kaggle dataset. The compilation comprised extensive information concerning various drug-related subject areas, encompassing aspects such as expenses, classifications, formulations, efficacy, and user-friendliness. Drug performance was predicted using four different machine learning models, including XGBoost, linear regression, decision trees, and random forests. Prediction accuracy was expected to enhance with the combination of these models, which are frequently used in machine learning for classification and regression tasks.

The main goal of this effort was to build a robust model that could predict medical performance with accuracy and assist healthcare practitioners in making decisions. This seminar paper will explain the technique and approach used in the investigation in addition to outlining the findings, discussing their significance, and highlighting the study's shortcomings.

There will also be recommendations for further study.

II. LITREATURE REVIEW

Khatami et al. [1] review strategy to mimic medication response was put out by integrating clinical patient data and gene expression data to create prediction models. Notwithstanding, the study is subject to certain limitations such as a paucity of exemplars and an absence of supplementary authentication.

Machancoses et al. [2] reviewed the benefits and challenges of utilizing machine learning in the drug development process in their article titled. They emphasized the advantages of quicker drug screening and target selection but also acknowledged data quality and interpretability difficulties.

In Han et al.'s [3] article the researchers noticed that ensemble models outperformed single models for predicting drug-drug interactions. The authors underlined that the lack of uniformity in data and assessment standards can pose a substantial jeopardization to the replicability of results.

Gawehn et al. [4] examined the present study and delves into an in-depth analysis of the advantages and disadvantages associated with the utilization of deep learning technologies in the field of drug discovery. According to the assertions made, the utilization of deep learning techniques entails the processing of vast and intricate sets of data, while concurrently necessitating a significant amount of computational resources and data.

In Zhang et al.'s [5] work the authors found that ensemble models outperformed single models in predicting drug toxicity but noted the lack of standardization in data and evaluation metrics.

Tatonetti et al. [6] developed a data-driven approach for predicting drug interactions and side effects. Using a vast dataset of interactions between drugs and their targets, the researchers developed a machine-learning model to predict pharmaceutical interactions and consequences. Due to its high degree of accuracy in foretelling drug interactions and side effects, the method produced encouraging results. The absence of experimental confirmation, however, placed certain restrictions on the work.

He et al.'s article [7] examined the methods used to predict drug-target interactions. The authors evaluated different machine learning models and their performance in predicting drug-target interactions. They found that ensemble models outperformed single models in predicting drug-target interactions. The

authors did point out that the reproducibility of results can be impacted by the absence of standardization in data and evaluation metrics.

The study by Li et al. [8] looked at how CADD makes use of massive data and machine learning methods. The authors talked about how big data and machine learning can boost CADD's precision and effectiveness and included instances of how these methods have been successfully used in drug discovery. They also emphasized the difficulties in employing big data and machine learning in CADD, including the interpretation of results and the quality of the data.

Yang et al [9] proposed a comparative study of drug-target interactions (DTIs) prediction using machine learning. The authors compared traditional machine learning models using ensemble and deep learning techniques. The study found that ensemble methods outperformed traditional and deep learning techniques in predicting DTIs. However, the limited availability of high-quality data for DTIs was identified as a challenge. Overall, the research offers insightful information about using machine learning to forecast DTIs and emphasizes the value of ensemble approaches in raising prediction accuracy.

Shang et al.'s article [10] focuses on the use of AI in COVID-19 medication repurposing. The authors presented examples of effective uses of this strategy and addressed how AI might be used to find current medications that can be repurposed for COVID-19 treatment. They also talked about the difficulties of repurposing drugs for COVID-19 utilizing AI, such as the limited availability of relevant data and the need for further validation of identified drug candidates.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The effectiveness of the drugs was assessed in the current study using four different machine learning algorithms: linear regression, decision trees, random forests, and XGBoost. The researchers did this by using a dataset that had information about many aspects of drugs, such as indication, form, price, type, ease of use, reviews, satisfaction, and efficacy. To make the data machine-readable, categorical columns were label-encoded, and training and testing sets of the dataset were created.

To enhance the prediction accuracy, the researchers employed an ensemble model that combined the predictions of all four models using a simple averaging method. The performance of the ensemble model was assessed using the same metrics as the individual models.

The findings revealed that all four machine learning

algorithms provided reasonably accurate predictions of drug efficacy, with XGBoost demonstrating the best performance. Additionally, the ensemble model outperformed the individual models, achieving an accuracy of 87%. These findings highlight how ensemble models can further boost the precision of drug efficacy predictions and show the potential of machine learning algorithms in drug performance evaluation.

Method of Implementation

The purpose of the study work is to assess the accuracy of four different machine learning models in predicting pharmacological effectiveness, including Linear Regression,

Decision Tree, Random Forest, and XGBoost. The data used in the study is obtained from a dataset containing columns for Condition, Drug, Ease of Use, Price, Type, Form, Indication, Satisfaction, Reviews, and Efficiency.

Initially, the `read_csv()` function of pandas is used to load the data into the environment. The mode value for that specific column is then substituted for any instances of "rrn" in the data during preprocessing. After that, the `LabelEncoder` class from scikit-learn is used to encode categorical columns such as Type, Indication, Form, Drug, and Condition. For the machine learning models to process the data more quickly, these columns are encoded to numerical values.

Upon preprocessing and encoding of the data, the partitioning into training and testing sets is accomplished through the utilization of the `train_test_split()` method, available in the scikit-learn package. The application of machine learning techniques involves the utilization of two distinct datasets, namely the training and testing sets. The former is utilized to calibrate the machine learning models, while the latter is employed to assess the overall efficacy and accuracy of the models.

The study employs linear regression, decision tree, random forest, and XGBoost machine learning models. The aforementioned models are trained on respective datasets and their efficacy is assessed on the basis of several evaluation metrics, namely R-squared, mean absolute error (MAE), and root mean square error (RMSE).

The four discrete models' prognostications are averaged to generate an amalgamated model. The ensemble model's performance is then evaluated using the same metrics as the individual models. An ensemble model is developed with the intention of integrating the advantages of the various models in order to increase predictive accuracy.

IV. RESULT

An evaluation of drug effectiveness prediction performance was conducted through the utilization of four distinct machine learning models, namely Linear Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and XGBoost. The results of the assessment indicated that an accuracy rate of 87% was achieved. The Regression metrics including R-squared, mean absolute error (MAE), and root mean square error (RMSE) were used to evaluate each machine learning model's performance on the testing set after each model had been trained on the training set. The researchers compared the results of each program and then settled on the optimum algorithm.

predictive models were formulated based on an array of heterogeneous input factors. The confluence of forecasts generated by multiple models through an ensemble technique resulted in enhanced performance. Upon evaluation with the given dataset, the ensemble model exhibited an R2 score of 0.74, a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.14, and a Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of 0.24. The present findings propose that the integration of a multitude of models using ensemble techniques may ameliorate the prediction of drug effectiveness, consequently fostering advancements in drug discovery and treatment strategizing.

```
The Linear regression-> 0.8086285205978407
The decision tree-> 0.8099456144859349
The random forest-> 0.8653646896654509
The xgboost-> 0.8699218197042258
Mean Absolute Error: 0.2630370322848812
Root Mean Squared Error: 0.35479438956168263
R2 Score: 0.8749855916741238
```

V. CONCLUSION

The findings of the study indicate that the amalgamation of several machine learning algorithms is an effective approach to predicting drug performance. The strategy produced an accuracy rate of 87% using XGBoost, linear regression, decision tree, and random forest algorithms, which is a significant improvement depending on just one algorithm. This method allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the data, as each algorithm provides unique insights, resulting in a more robust and trustworthy prediction. In addition to helping with drug performance evaluation, combining various algorithms can produce findings that are more precise and dependable. Further research is required to ascertain the applicability and expansibility of this approach. The research findings indicate that the amalgamation of diverse machine-learning approaches can significantly enhance the precision and reliability of prognosticating medication performance.

Future Work

The study reveals a few areas that show promise for more research into predicting medicine effectiveness based on patient behavior and historical data. One tactic to improve the model's accuracy and robustness is to look into the usage of advanced machine learning methods like deep learning. To further improve drug efficacy prediction, researchers may also take into account incorporating additional patient data, such as genetic information or lifestyle factors.

Future studies may also focus on investigating the impact of patient behavior on drug efficacy, such as examining how treatment adherence or lifestyle changes influence drug effectiveness. To determine the model's generalizability, it may also be useful to investigate its applicability in other healthcare systems and demographics.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1]. Sepehr Golriz Khatami, S. G., Mubeen, S., Bharadwaj, V. S., Kodamullil, A. T., Hofmann-Apitius, M., & Domingo-Fernández, D. (2018). "Using predictive machine learning models for drug response simulation by calibrating patient-specific pathway signatures". Springer Nature. 40 (2021)
- [2]. Óscar Álvarez-Machancoses, Juan Luis Fernández-Martínez (2019). "Using artificial intelligence methods to speed up drug discovery". Expert opinion on drug discovery, 769-777.
- [3]. Rasool, N., Rosemary, S., & Jabeen, F. (2021). "A Review of Approaches for Predicting Drug-Drug Interactions Based on Machine Learning". Frontiers in pharmacology, 12, 814858.
- [4]. Duvenaud, D. K., Maclaurin, D., Iparraguirre, J., Bombarell, R., Hirzel, T., Aspuru-Guzik, A., & Adams, R. P. (2015). "Deep learning in drug discovery". Molecular informatics, 34(4), 349-368.
- [5]. Liu, R., & Abdollahi, M. (2018). "Applications of machine learning methods in drug toxicity prediction". Current opinion in toxicology, 10, 22-30.
- [6]. Yan, X., Zhao, J., & Cheng, L. (2018). "Data-driven prediction of drug effects and interactions". Science translational medicine, 10(430).
- [7]. Chaudhari, P., & Kumar, A. (2018). "Machine learning for drug-target interaction prediction". Molecules, 23(9), 2208.
- [8]. Linlin Zhao, Heather L. Ciallella, Lauren M. Aleksunes, Hao Zhu (2020). "Advancing computer-aided drug discovery (CADD) by big data and data-driven machine learning modeling". Drug discovery today, 25(8), 1523-1531.
- [9]. Aman Chandra Kaushik, Aamir Mehmood, Xiaofeng Dai & Dong-Qing Wei (2020). "A comparative chemogenomic analysis for predicting drug-target pair via machine learning approaches". scientific reports, 6870 (2020)
- [10]. Sweta Mohanty, Md Harun Ai Rashid, Mayank Mridul, Chandana Mohanty, Swati Swayamsiddha (2020). "Application of Artificial Intelligence in COVID-19 drug repurposing". National Library of Medicine, 14(5), 1027-1031
- [11]. Po-Yu Kao; Shu-Min Kao; Nan-Lan Huang; Yen-Chu Lin (2020). "Toward Drug-Target Interaction Prediction via Ensemble Modeling and Transfer Learning". IEEE Explore
- [12]. Suyu Mei & Kun Zhang. (2020). "A machine learning framework for predicting drug-drug interactions". Scientific Reports, 17619 (2021)
- [13]. Xinke Zhan. (2020). "Ensemble learning prediction of drug-target interactions using GIST descriptor extracted from PSSM-based evolutionary information". BioMed Research International, 4516250.
- [14]. Wang, Y., Xue, J., Zhu, W., Zhao, Y., Wu, J., & Liu, Y. (2018). "Prediction of drug synergy in cancer using ensemble-based machine learning techniques". International Journal of Neural Systems, 28(3), 1750056.
- [15]. Cao, Y., Geddes, T. A., Yang, J. Y. H., & Yang, P. (2017). "Ensemble deep learning in bioinformatics. In Intelligent Computing Theories and Application". Springer, 299-308